

AquaPLAN

Aquatic Pollution from Light and Anthropogenic Noise: **Management of Impacts on Biodiversity**

D3.1 Harmonized protocols for quantifying LNP conditions in aquatic systems

11/11/24 Version 2.3

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The AquaPLAN project promises to establish the first long term monitoring survey of the biological impacts of light and noise pollution (LNP) across European aquatic ecosystems. Observational field studies of the combined impacts of LNP have not previously been attempted, providing no baseline to guide investigators towards a harmonised monitoring approach.

In this deliverable, we provide a summary of methods that could be used by researchers/managers to start monitoring LNP in aquatic systems. The deliverable is not meant to exhaustively explain physical properties of light and noise. It aims to function as an easy-to-use guidance to start exploring this field.

We list the response variables that can be measured, the main instruments that can be used and our suggestions for performing the monitoring. We also indicate the best periods to do the measurements and the additional variables that should be taken to archive with the measurements and that are necessary to interpret the results.

The deliverable is connected to D3.3 and D4.1, which focus on monitoring the impact of LNP on biota and on the design of manipulative experiments to test cause-effect relationships between LNP and biological variables.

D3.1 will serve as a reference for field surveys in general and, as specified in the text of D 3.3 it will be a guidance for AquaPLAN scientists and lead to the completion of D 3.9 “*Database of ecological time series (spanning at least three years) relating biodiversity changes to LNP conditions (including EBVs responses and data on stressors)*” and D3.10 “*Report (including crossed-system analyses) on results on potential impacts of LNP on rivers, lakes, temperate and tropical coastal systems*”.

D3.1 has been prepared in collaboration with all AquaPLAN investigators involved in the collection of biological data in field monitoring (Task 3.3). A series of meetings were held in the first 6 months of the AquaPLAN project to agree on a strategy towards Deliverables 3.1 and 3.3 (see text in D3.3 for more details).

Disclaimer: The document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including its associated Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial light and anthropogenic noise are important and emergent pollutants for aquatic ecosystems. AquaPLAN project's main objective is to understand the effect of the co-occurrence of these pollutants on aquatic biodiversity and propose effective mitigation solutions. Within this framework, the protocol here aims at providing a comprehensive easy-to-use toolkit to define a protocol of measurements of the intensity and type of these pollutants.

In aquatic coastal and riverine ecosystems light pollution mainly originates from the coast as fixed light points such as streetlamps in ports or nearby cities, whereas noise pollution is in most cases originated by navigation of small vessels and large cargos and, for shallow and intertidal areas from in-air noise such as land and air transports, or industries. In offshore sites, cargo navigation, extraction platforms and wind farms may represent important, often disregarded, sources of both light and noise pollution.

Both light and noise are physical waves whose detection strongly depends on the right choice of instruments (e.g. sensitivity, capacity to detect intensity within the target bandwidth, duration of the measurement). In the context of light pollution, measurements are mainly done as intensity of the entire visible spectrum or by analysing specific wavelengths at night, when natural light is at its minimum. Noise pollution detection is instead often part of the analysis of the ambient sound or soundscape. The soundscape includes all the sounds that can be perceived by human ears. These sounds can be roughly classified into three large categories depending on the main sources: **biophony**: when sound originated from animals using sounds for communicating or just making sounds while moving or eating; **geophony**: includes the natural sounds related to non-living items, such as earthquakes, storms, rolling of rocks etc.; **anthrophony**: it is the sound produced by human activities and it is the one addressed as Noise pollution.

2. BASIC PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF LIGHT AND SOUND AND LIST OF VARIABLES THAT CAN BE CONSIDERED

2.1 LIGHT POLLUTION

There are mainly 2 types of physical variables that can be measured for detecting the level of light pollution (**Table 1**):

- **Photometric variables:** they deal with the measurement of light in terms of its perceived brightness to the human eye. These measures can focus on directional and non-directional light intensity and are measured using Candela or luminance. In addition to physical variables, a largely used astronomical variable is night sky brightness measured as “magnitudes per square arcsecond” (mag arcsec^{-2}). It is used to quantify the skyglow aspect of light pollution since skyglow reduces night sky brightness. Skyglow is the diffuse luminance of the night sky and, in the context of light pollution, refers to the luminance originating from artificial light sources propagating into the atmosphere and partially scattered back to the ground. The light scattering causing skyglow is due to molecules such as N_2 and O_2 and aerosols, especially in urban areas.
- **Radiometric variables:** they deal with the measurement of energy per time (= power, given in watts) emitted by light sources or impinging on a particular surface. Thus, the units of all radiometric quantities are based on watts (W).

Table 1. Type of measurements for detecting light level.

	Measurement	Unit	Description
Photometric	Candela	Cd	The luminous power emitted by a light source per unit solid angle
	Luminance	Cd m^{-2}	The amount of light emitted or reflected from an object per unit area
	Illuminance	lux	Brightness to human eye
	Luminance	mag arcsec^{-2}	Night sky brightness per second
Radiometric	Irradiance	$\text{Wm}^{-2} (\text{nm}^{-1})$	Power received by a surface per unit area
	Radiance	$\text{Wsr}^{-1}\text{m}^{-2} (\text{nm}^{-1})$	Power emitted, reflected or received per unit solid angle

2.2 NOISE POLLUTION

Sound level can be measured mainly by considering its wave aspect, whereas it is very difficult to evaluate particle motion, despite the fact that it might be important for determining the sensitivity of several organisms to noise pollution. However, particle motion can be calculated indirectly from sound pressure measurements. The validity of this approximation depends on detailed knowledge of various factors, including the distance to the sound source, proximity of sea surface and seabed boundaries that could impact wave propagation, size of the sound source, cut-off frequency, wavelength of the sound, and variation in sound propagation. Below the main measurements used for sound level characterisation (**Table 2**):

- **Power spectral density (PSD):** It measures how signal power is distributed with frequency. Mean power spectral density is obtained by dividing the mean squared pressure for each frequency band by its bandwidth. To calculate power spectral density levels (PSDL), mean spectral power density needs to be converted to dB. The reference value for mean squared pressure levels is $1 \mu\text{Pa}^2/\text{Hz}$. PSDL can be determined over varying frequency (e.g., 1 Hz bands) and time scales (e.g., hourly, daily, monthly, annually). Since it expresses average signal levels within the spectral

band, it is suitable for representing amplitudes of broadband, continuous sound (e.g., wind or ship sounds), but for narrowband tones the values will vary with the width of the measurement band, and it would be better to measure the sound pressure waveform directly

- **Sound Pressure level (SDL):** It measures the amplitude of the sound across frequency bands. Sound pressure levels underwater is measured as dB relative to the reference pressure of 1 μPa for a specified frequency range over a stated time interval. SPL can be expressed as Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) or as Third-Octave Band (TOB). TOB is a frequency band consisting of one-third of an octave. This is appropriate for most considerations of the environmental impact of noise. TOB helps to focus on low frequency, especially 63 and 125 (~most affected by navigation of large vessels).

Table 2. Type of variables to detect sound level.

Measurement	Unit	Description
Power Spectral density	dB re 1 $\mu\text{Pa}^2/\text{Hz}$.	PSD is the mean-square sound-pressure spectral density
Sound Pressure Level (SPL)	dB re 1 μPa	The reference value of SPL for sound in water is 1 μPa , leading to SPL being expressed in dB re 1 μPa . The averaging time used in the calculation of the values of SPL will be 10 s.

3. MAIN INSTRUMENTS USED FOR MEASURING LNP IN AQUATIC SYSTEMS

In order to plan a monitoring LNP it is necessary to have an idea of the main devices that could be used for this monitoring. We provide here an overview of these instruments in 2 large tables (**Table 3** and **Table 4**).

3.1 LIGHT POLLUTION

Researchers often measure light on sea surface and run spot measurements. Measuring artificial light underwater is complex and at present a very limited number of instruments exists that can be immersed and able to take measurements over a relatively long-term period.

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Table 3. Some of the devices that can be used to measure light and their main characteristics.

Type of Instrument	Measure	Resolution	Applications	Underwater measure available	Cost	Availability
Spectrometer	Irradiance Reflectance	Hyperspectral	Spot measurement Skyglow (QE Pro only)	No	>1 5K	UOP, FVB
Oceanographic Radiometer	Irradiance	Multispectral	Spot measurement; vertical profile, Skyglow	Yes	>100K	UOP
	Irradiance	Broadband	Spot measurement; mapping; data logging Skyglow	Yes	1-5K	UOP
	Irradiance	Multispectral	RGB Skyglow	Yes	<1K	UOP, FBV
Sky Quality Meter	Night sky brightness	n/a	Spot measurement datalogging Skyglow	No	<1K	UOP, SZN, FBV, ULEI
Lux meter	Illuminance	n/a	Spot measurement Skyglow	Yes (with appropriate probe)	<1K	UOP, SZN, FBV
HOBO Light data logger	Illuminance	n/a	Datalogging (>5lx applications)	Yes	<0.1K	UOP, UNIP1
Sky quality camera	Illuminance	n/a	Spot measurements. Customized DLSR system requires calibration Skyglow	No	<1K	FBV, ULEI
LANcube flatLAN	Illuminance	Multispectral	RGB	In progress	<1K	UNIP1

3.2 NOISE POLLUTION

Noise can be recorded continuously underwater with both high- and low-quality hydrophones, manually for short-term assessments or coupled to loggers for long-term assessments. Hydrophone recordings can be used to monitor average amplitude levels and amplitude fluctuations in time.

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Table 4. Some of the devices that can be used to measure noise underwater and their main characteristics.

Type of Instrument	Sensibility (Frequency bandwidth)	Main application and depth	Data acquisition system (DAQ)	Cost	Availability in the consortium
Single analogue hydrophone	10 Hz- 800 kHz	Daily Underwater acoustic measurements 0-6000m	To be used with a preamplifier and an input module (examples: handy recorder or sound acquisition board)	>1 5K	SZN
Single digital hydrophone	10 Hz - 200 kHz	Daily Underwater acoustic measurements 0-6000m	Stand alone	5-10K	SZN
Autonomous recorder	10 Hz - 400 kHz	Long-term (monthly) monitoring of ambient noise 0-3000m	Stand-alone - to be used with batteries. During deep deployments need an acoustic release	5-20K	SZN, UNIPI
Towed array of hydrophones	10 Hz - 150 kHz	Dynamic and on-board acoustic monitoring - are usually >1 sensor for daily sound measures direction to the depth of 0-500 m	To be used with an input module	15-30K	SZN
Autonomous observation systems (example: glider)	10 Hz - 150 kHz	Large scale and long-term (monthly) monitoring of ambient noise 0-1000 m	Dedicated DAQ system	>100K	SZN
Cabled station	10 Hz - 150 kHz	Real-time and long-term (annual) monitoring to the 0-6000 m	Dedicated DAQ system	>50K	
Surface buoy	10 Hz - 150 kHz	Real-time and/or long-term monitoring for shallow waters (0-20 m)	Dedicated DAQ system	>20K	SZN
Drifting Buoy	10 Hz - 150 kHz	Large-scale monitoring for daily measures in shallow waters (0-10 m)	Dedicated DAQ system		
Biologging Tag	10 Hz - 150 kHz	Daily monitoring on animals.	Stand alone	>5K	SZN
HydroMoth MEMS device (underwater)	10 Hz - 400 kHz	Underwater acoustic measurement For noise event detection.	Stand alone	<1K <200	ULEI
AudioMoth MEMS device (in-air)	10 Hz - 400 kHz	In-air acoustic measurements, noise event detection (used in conjunction with hydromoths).	Stand alone	<200	ULEI
AudioMoth MEMS device (in-air)	20kHz	In-air acoustic measurements, noise event detection (used in conjunction with hydromoths).	Stand alone	200	ULEI
Soundtraps	20 Hz - 60 kHz	Underwater acoustic measurements absolute noise measurements of the soundscapes.	Stand alone	4000	ULEI, IMR

4. HOW TO USE THE DEVICES AND ADDITIONAL VARIABLES TO MEASURE

The choice of the devices to use for measuring light and noise and of the additional measures is an essential step for LNP monitoring. In particular, additional information should help to interpret the data and, in some cases, work as proxies for LNP. In **Table 5** we summarise how AquaPLAN monitoring will make use of these devices and measure additional variables.

Before starting to monitor it is necessary:

- to get acquainted with the main sources of pollution for the area;
- to gather information on when and where these sources are important on a local scale;
- to check for existing light and noise maps for large scale putative LNP existence and intensity (see D3.3 section 4 for more details);
- to identify the source(s) in need to be measured and choose the most adapted devices to get the information.

During measurements, always take note of the date, time and GPS location of the measurements for LNP.

4.1 LIGHT

Measurements should:

- be conducted during the night according to the moon phase, giving priority to new moon conditions. Times of sunrise and sunset, moonrise and moonset, and the illumination of the lunar disk can be obtained via www.timeanddate.com or using the Astropy package (Python and R). More details are in D3.3.
- include ancillary meteorological conditions which may greatly affect skyglow. As a minimum, these should be the cloud coverage (as a percentage, or oktas) and an estimate of cloud height.
- Include water turbidity, possibly chlorophyll concentration, suspended particulate material (SPM), and coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM). Since most instruments for LP can be used on land but not underwater, these measures may help understanding light penetration into the water.

4.1 NOISE

Particle motion (a part of the sound together with sound pressure) is what most aquatic animals use for extracting information about their environment. Although this is not measured, in far-field and open-water conditions sound pressure and particle motion are linearly related. In shallow waters, however, close to the bottom, the relationship becomes more complicated. Thus, it is necessary to keep into consideration this phenomenon when filtering the data. Applications of particle motion sensors to passive acoustic monitoring would be suggested when available. We are confident it will emerge in the future. The other information to gather is listed below. available. We are confident it will emerge in the future. The other information to gather is listed below.

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Measurements should:

- allow to distinguish between anthrophony and the naturally present baseline ambient noise (geophony and biophony).
- estimate water depth, sediment type, and chemical composition, as well as the condition of nearby reflective surfaces of rocks. All these factors can in fact impact sound propagation and as such the measurements of both the amplitude and spectral content of sound sources
- measure the weather-related state of the water surface. In fact, viscosity and sound propagation are influenced by temperature and salinity, which are therefore important variables to record.
- annotate substrate complexity. Some habitats, such as shallow ones, require a characterization of substrate complexity and composition together with the bathymetry to understand and model sound propagation.
- report, when appropriate, the river width, as well as waterflow (including the one generated by tides) that impact the propagation of sound across the water body.
- annotate air temperature for intertidal areas since this influences sound transmission through air due to atmospheric absorption (esp. high frequencies) and sound refraction. For noise pollution originating in air such as traffic noise, temperature measurements are therefore useful.

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Table 5. Metadata to be collected during monitoring surveys. This table is complementary to Table in D3.3.

Partners	Ecosystem	Location(s)	Light	Noise	Sampling design
UOP	Temperate intertidal rocky shores	Plymouth Sound, UK Falmouth Bay, UK	Spectrometer, sky quality meter+luxmeter (at night)	AudioMoth (or other in-air recorders)	sites of low and high artificial light close and far from cargo trajectories
UNIPI, SZN	Subtidal macroalgae and seagrass	Tuscan and Ligurian coasts, Italy	sky quality meter luxmeter LANCube/ flatLAN (at night and underwater for flatLAN)	Underwater autonomous recorder	Mainly in MPA, sites of low and high artificial light close and far from small vessels passages
BIU	Tropical subtidal ecosystems	Gulf of Aqaba, Israel	Spectrometer, sky quality meter+luxmeter (at night)	Underwater autonomous recorder	Across the latitudinal gradient of Aqaba, sites of different light and noise pollution
ULEI	Temperate rivers	Dutch rivers	Sky quality meter HOBO	AudioMoth +HydroMoth+Underwater autonomous recorders	across the river gradient, according to fixed light points and cargos
FVB	Temperate lakes	German lakes	Sky Quality Camera	Underwater autonomous recorder	Vertical distribution of LNP according to the movement of zooplankton

5. APPLICATION TO SOME AQUATIC SYSTEMS

This section illustrates some examples for aquatic systems on **how to conduct the LNP monitoring**. The example includes some suggestions specific for the habitat, but most suggestions can be easily applied to other systems. Monitoring should be conducted in locations characterised by contrasting conditions of high and low levels/no pollution (related to ALAN and noise), to be able to create comparative data at similar environmental conditions. It is also important to always identify the ecological system of interest and the biological scale(s) at which the impact should be measured. It is indeed important to monitor at locations relevant to the study species and at the spatial and temporal scales that are likely to impact most often the biological system chosen. The placement of the device is also fundamental. For light, the mosaics of light and shadows should be considered and the device positioned to collect representative data (e.g., maximum and minimum light intensity or mean light intensity). For sound, the recorder should be placed to avoid as much as possible the tide- or river-generated current flow or at least annotate additional information in order to filter data *a posteriori*. The system used to attach the instrument might also be a source of data distortion: it could shadow the light sensors or be an additional sound source. Any loose chains or mechanical collisions among deployment components with currents or surf should be avoided when measuring sound.

Temperature, whether conditions, salinity, moon phase, turbidity of the water and all other ancillary variables illustrated above should be recorded.

5.1 COASTAL MARINE HABITATS

In coastal areas, the main sources of light and noise pollution originate from land illumination and navigation of small vessels or cargos, respectively.

For **Light monitoring**, in intertidal habitats spotlight measurements should be taken at night during low tide. For shallow subtidal habitats, in addition to aerial nocturnal measurements, it is suggested to include spotlight measurements underwater by using transparent (i.e., capable of blocking the least quantity and quality of light) underwater cases for protecting the instrument(s). Measurements should be taken according to the lunar phase, by prioritising new moon conditions; additional measurements under different moon phases are suggested (e.g., full moon condition). Given the likely variability in human activities (e.g. tourism) among seasons, it is suggested to stratify the sampling across seasons.

For **Noise monitoring**, recorders should be preferably anchored to the sea bottom, using frames. Each frame should be equipped with a single recorder or double channel autonomous recorders. Alternatively, recorders could fluctuate in the water column near the bottom using a simple mooring composed of 1) ballast; 2) autonomous recorder; 3) buoy. In all cases, be careful that the system used does not produce noise itself. The autonomous recorders can be programmed to measure noise continuously or using duty cycles, which may considerably save batteries, allow longer periods of recording and also save time when retrieving data from the recorder. Continuous acquisition is preferable for acoustic monitoring of ambient noise, but a duty cycle of 5 min every 30 min is reasonable to collect long-term data for noise pollution and ambient noise.

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During summer 2024, the protocol for detecting light and noise pollution was tested by the UNIPI/SZN joint team within *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, one of the subtidal habitats listed within AquaPLAN as a model system for coastal habitats.

Autonomous recorders (10 Hz - 400 kHz) were placed at 10m depth within the *Posidonia* meadow but avoiding the edges. The deployments lasted for a 3–4-week period, as a compromise between the batteries' life duration and the set recording duty-cycle (5 mins on - 25 mins off). We expected to record noise up to 1000m distance from the source. We positioned one hydrophone per meadow. To stabilise and ensure the anchoring of each hydrophone, a custom-made plastic ballast case was built and weighted down >10kg using diving weights (Fig. 1). Both deployment and retrieval were done by divers. Diurnal light (lux) and daily temperature (°C) at each site were recorded every 30 mins by Hobo loggers anchored to the ballast case.

Figure 1 Picture of the hydrophone deployed over a seagrass bed using the plastic ballast case

Figure 2 FlatLAN embedded with the underwater case before being deployed

When the meadow was in proximity of fixed sources of light (streetlamps), the illuminance for the 3 wavelengths (RGB) was measured by positioning the flatLAN under the main light source on land and close to the water surface, at night under new moon condition. The flatLAN was originally built to measure light pollution inland, therefore waterproof caseless. Provided with an underwater case, the flatLAN was submerged just over the meadow at around 6 metre depth: the instrument was left for an entire night hanging over the meadow when possible, or positioned

on the seafloor within the meadow, with the sensor looking upwards the water surface (Fig. 2). Unfortunately, low light intensity reaching the bottom was not detected by the cased instrument, due to its current sensitivity. At present, the UNIPI team is collaborating with physicists and technologists to increase the sensitivity of the instrument.

5.2 RIVER SYSTEMS

In rivers, the sources of light and noise pollution include boat traffic and artificial illumination of infrastructures (roads, bridges, buildings). For light monitoring, the same caution illustrated above should apply. For noise pollution, we highlight here the importance of the placement of the hydrophone to avoid unwanted noise. Recorders should be positioned in the water column and distant from the shore. Note that in tidal river areas the position in the water column can fluctuate. We suggest continuously recording Sound Traps for soundscape. A cheaper alternative to Soundtraps are Hydromoths (Fig. 3), underwater acoustic recorders. They record at low resolution but can be deployed at greater numbers and across more locations. This approach is particularly useful when one wants to measure specific noise events (such

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Figure 3 Hydromoth suspended on rope with hydrophone

Figure 4 Audiomoth attached to a tree on the riverside

as traffic), assess sound propagation over distance (for example traffic noise from bridges), or measure noise events or animal activity that occurs at specific times of day/night. Hydromoths can also be coupled with in-air acoustic recorders (audiomoths, songmeters). The recording period depends on when the animals are active, and when the noise pollution occurs. To assess cyclical anthropogenic noise such as traffic, recordings should be made for 7+ days. When assessing diurnal animal activity patterns, it can be sufficient to record during the time of day/night the animals are active, or at the activity peak.

During May 2024, the protocol for detecting noise pollution was tested in rivers in Germany and Belgium close to their delta by the UNILEI team.

Songmeter/audiomoth (in-air) and hydromoths (underwater) were used to detect noise events and placed in air 1.50-2m above waterline and in water at 1-3m depth (at low tide). The instruments were left overnight (8h) with a duty cycle of 60 min recordings. The songmeters/audiomoths (Fig. 4) were attached to structures at riverbank (streetlamps, railings, trees), with the microphone pointing at the river. The hydromoths were attached to a brick when placed on a riverbank. When placed in sluices, they were attached to sluice walls or dangling off sluice ladders using a rope weighed down by a brick with the microphones pointing at the middle of the river. The affordable price of these instruments allows exploring the area of interest and gathering information on how many noise events may occur. It is important to select the deployment sites very carefully; to avoid disturbances close to the microphone caused by biophony or geophony, such as noisy trees or sites where noisy animals gather that are not the target of the recordings.

The light was measured using HOBOS to detect the natural light cycle. HOBOS cannot be used for artificial light. They were placed 1.50-2m above the waterline, attached to structures at the riverbank (streetlamps, railings, trees).

6. DATA MANAGEMENT

- All data will be collected and curated in accordance with the AquaPLAN Data Management Plan outlined in D1.4.
- Data shall be stored in a secure location until made available to the AquaPLAN consortium and the public as per the Data Management Plan.

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- All data collected as part of the monitoring surveys shall be collected in a central database that is made available to the AquaPLAN consortium by month 40 (D3.9).
- Project participants who intend to disseminate their results must give at least 15 calendar days prior notice to other project participants (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they intend to disseminate (GA Article 17 – Annex 5; CA - paragraph 8.4.2 Dissemination of own (including jointly owned) Results; D6.1 PDEC - paragraph 2.2.4 Communication and Dissemination of Results)

7. ETHICS

The AquaPLAN Ethics guidelines are outlined in D1.2. Ethics review will not be required for the collection of LNP.

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